

Research Article

Strengthening Project Guidance Advocacy and Building Adherence of the Youth (GABAY) of San Pascual Senior High School 1 through Needs Assessment Inventory Survey Among Grade 11 Students

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Abstract: The Needs Assessment Inventory Survey for San Pascual Senior High School 1 Students is constructed to be administered to Grade 11 Senior High School students and know their needs and its importance. Guidance is an integral part of education catered to offer assistance to individuals so that they would make intelligent decisions and adjustments in life. This data analysis will use descriptive documentary research method. Documentary analysis involves the gathering of information by analyzing written records and documents to solve a problem. The results revealed that the San Pascual Senior High school 1 Grade 11 students have the least focus on the student's Academic/Self-Development. The Guidance Intervention Program is of great help for the improvement on the three domains; Career Development, Personal/Social, and Academic/Self Development Domain that should be implemented and executed by the Guidance Office.

Keywords: Needs Assessment, Guidance, Guidance Intervention Program.

Introduction

Holistic education is believed to be the ideal view of nurturing students nowadays along with the visions of K12 education. Schools are the expected avenues to cater student's needs in all aspects to achieve a lifelong learning with a formal education. However, with the present condition that society experiences today, various changes, difficulties and problems intervene with the conventional way of living. Education sector, as one of the important agencies in delivering quality of life in the country, has shifted to various adjustments to maintain quality education for the students despite of the threats of pandemic. In connection with this, one of the foreseen problems regarding students' learning is the ability of the students to discern the valid, reliable and necessary skills needed for them to gain and establish knowledge despite of this global problem. The Department of Education issued Deped Order no. 18 series of 2020 which covers the Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Learning Continuity Plan. This Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-CLP) aims to ensure that learning opportunities are provided to learners in safe manner, through different learning delivery.

San Pascual Senior High School 1 is aware that even before the pandemic, there are many problems that existed including drop outs, absenteeism, cutting classes, bullying and many other things that

affect students' academic success. Thus, the guidance office believes that with the present education set-up, these problems may also arise and affect their learning in the modular distance approach. Advisers, teachers, and all education practitioners are responsible in shaping and nurturing the lives of the students, since school is the second home of the students where he enhances learning. To achieve these, there is a need to focus on students' development domains.

Lev Vygotsky, a known psychologist, proposed a seminal learning theory that has gone on to become very influential, especially in the field of education. Like Piaget, Vygotsky believed that children learn actively and through hands-on experiences. His sociocultural theory also suggested that parents, caregivers, peers and the culture at large were responsible for developing higher order functions. In Vygotsky's view, learning is an inherently social process. Through interacting with others, learning becomes integrated into an individual's understanding of the world. This child development theory also introduced the concept of the zone of proximal development, which is the gap between what a person can do with help and what they can do on their own. It is with the help of more knowledgeable others that people are able to progressively learn and increase their skills and scope of understanding.

Different Theories of development can be adopted in this study since the aim of the study is to develop the students holistically. Social Cognitive Theory contributes to an understanding of classroom management by providing techniques to help students self-regulate their behavior. These techniques are sometimes referred to as cognitive behavioral interventions. Appreciative Advising approach emphasizes the importance of relationships and seeking holistic understandings of students. These can be complimented nicely by an understanding the "Zone of Proximal Development" theory, and Dewey's emphasis on personal experience. Advising teachers were important in the Crookston's (1972) theory focuses on the relationship between the student and advisor and also the roles for each. Bloom's (2008) Appreciative Advising approach also emphasizes the importance of relationships and seeking holistic understandings of students. These can be complemented nicely by an understanding of Vygotsky's (1978) "Zone of Proximal Development" theory, as well as by Dewey's (1938) emphasis on personal experience.

Realized that arise innovative actions, teacher needs to know not only what to teach in school but also how to understand his students in order for him to teach effectively. Making provisions for better understanding of the individual learner and coping with his learning style is the present trend in education. So much so that we need to know how guidance can help in actualizing this recent educational concept. Guidance is an integral part of education catered to offer assistance to individuals so that they would make intelligent decisions and adjustments in life. Its fundamental aim is to help a person enhance the best in him—to help a person responsibly adjust to situations as he progresses. Furthermore, guidance is to see through oneself. By becoming familiar with one's interests and capabilities, the person is led to learn more about himself.

In the context of this study, the researcher intended to make a Needs Assessment Inventory Survey which will help them to strengthen Project Guidance Advocacy and Building Adherence of the Youth (GABAY) which main point is to give holistic education aligned with guidance advocacy, stakeholder's linkages, instructional leadership of teachers, and disaster and health crisis management and readiness in light of COVID 19. The Needs Assessment Inventory Survey for SPSHS 1 Students is constructed to be administered to grade 11 senior high school students and know their needs and its importance. It consist of three domains; Academic/Self Development Domain, Career Development Domain and Personal/Social Domain.

Findings in this study will be used as springboard for improving project GABAY to adjust the pressing needs of the students as they engage themselves in learning in the modular distance learning. This could help the school to take measure and adjust the School Improvement Plan (SIP). Adhering to the vow of commitment and dedication to the teaching profession and the vision and

mission of the Department of Education, this this will be a good avenue in uplifting the quality of education and services provided by the San Pascual Senior High School 1 Guidance personnel. Moreover, it will be an efficient tool in screening the students and help them understand themselves, improve their skills and interests, and eventually become a well-adjusted individual.

Research Questions

1. How may the students’ described their needs based on degree of Importance on different domains relative to.
 - 1.1 Academic/Self Development Domain;
 - 1.2 Career Development Domain; and
 - 1.3 Personal/Social Development?
2. What Guidance Program can be proposed based from the result of the study?

Methodology

A. Participants

In this study, the researcher uses random selection of population of grade 11 students of San Pascual Senior High School 1 during the A.Y. 2020-2021 from different strands; STEM, HUMSS, EIM, FBS ABM.

B. Data Gathering Method

This data analysis used descriptive documentary research method. Documentary analysis involves the gathering of information by analyzing written records and documents to solve a problem (Adanza, *et al.*, 2009). The researcher believed that the needs assessment survey can foretell the focus of Guidance Programs in the holistic development of the students. The researcher used random selection of population of grade 11 students of San Pascual Senior High School 1 from different strand. A self-constructed Needs Assessment Inventory Survey for SPSHS 1 Students is used to gather data.

Results and Discussions

1) Students’ assessment on their needs and degree of importance relative to different domains

Table 1.1. Academic/Self Development Domain

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Find time to finish assignments and socialize.	4.65	Very Important
Develop confidence in recitations and discussions.	4.65	Very Important
Talk to teacher about difficulty in understanding lesson.	4.47	Important
Balance between work at home and studies.	4.56	Very Important
Work with classmates on projects.	4.38	Important
Cope with financial demands of subjects.	4.29	Important
Manage my time.	4.79	Very Important
Discover my talents and develop them.	4.51	Very Important
Get rid of personal vices/uncontrollable habits (drugs, alcohol stealing, violence, smoking, sex, gambling, computer addiction.	3.87	Moderate Important
Know and understand myself better	4.78	Very Important
Composite Mean	4.49	Important

The table shows that the students view academic/self-development domain as important with a composite mean of 4.49. They consider various indicators as very important including their ways of

finding time to finish assignments and socialize, develop confidence in recitations and discussions, balancing between work at home and studies, managing their time and discovering their talents and how they are going to develop them. These results implies that students look at academic practices as very important since it could nurture their whole personality as it is the foundation of knowledge to progress towards higher level of learning. Meanwhile, some factors related to academic and self-development were viewed as important and it encompasses on the way they are going to deal with teachers and classmates especially in different academic engagements.

Table 1.2. Career Development Domain

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Discover for what work/occupation my talents and abilities could be useful.	4.76	Very Important
Discover in what work and occupation my interests and inclinations can be satisfied.	4.68	Very Important
Discover my values and in what course/occupation they would be most satisfied.	4.71	Very Important
Help me discover what other skills I need to develop for my chosen course/occupation.	4.67	Very Important
Help me overcome fears/doubts about my chosen course/occupation	4.75	Very Important
Composite Mean	4.71	Very Important

The table indicates that the students described career development domain as very important with a composite mean of 4.71. Discover for what work/occupation my talents and abilities could be useful. They give high regards to tasks related on discovering their possible work/occupation based on their talents and abilities. Students’ interests, values, fears/doubts are found to be considered as very important factors that they consider in choosing their future careers. The findings can be interpreted that students in Grade 11 are starting already to think critically and give so much attention about their possible career as they finish basic education years. Thus, this factor may be given attention and rigid guidance in order for them to choose which path suits them.

Table 1.3. Personal/Social Domain

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Know how to choose friends.	4.54	Very Important
Get rid of fear of social situations.	4.31	Important
Settle quarrels with/among friends.	4.31	Important
Handle peer pressure.	4.48	Important
Deal effectively with bullies.	4.22	Important
Develop the ability to discuss problems with parents.	4.59	Very Important
Balance between warrings/separated parents	4.24	Important
Develop the abilities to socialize with others harmoniously.	4.55	Very Important
Cope with the expectations/demands of parents	4.39	Important
Improve my relationship with my stepparent/siblings (please underline)	4.49	Important
Composite Mean	4.41	Important

It can be gleaned on the table that students assessed their personal/social domain as important especially their relationships with the people around them. Socializing with others harmoniously and having enough knowledge in choosing groups to fit in were described to be very important. It is an evident that students in their middle childhood years, they will always find a way to look for a place or group where they are comfortable with. Along with these, connection with parents, their family status and means of discussing problems with them are also regarded as very important. It was then followed by the idea that students have the ability to cope up with problems among with their friends and parents. Settling quarrels with friends, ways to deal with bullies in schools and responding and giving attention to the demands and requests of the parents are described to be important.

Analysis of the scores obtained from the Needs Assessment Inventory Survey among San Pascual Senior High School Students reveals that San Pascual Senior High School 1 Grade 11 students have a high score in Career Development Domain with a rating of 4.71, Personal/Social Domain, 4.41 and Academic/Self Development Domain 4.49. As the table revealed, San Pascual Senior High School 1 Grade 11 students score in the Career Development Domain with a rating of 4.71 which means the focus of their needs and importance is on that domain. These result suggests that San Pascual Senior High School 1 Grade 11 students' approaches in career improvement and to effectively respond on this, a guidance program centered on career development may be proposed.

2) Proposed Action Plan

Based on the findings, the students consider academic/self-development domain, career development domain, and personal/social development domain as determinants of their holistic development. However, among these, they consider career development domain as very important. In this point, a guidance program focussing on career development domain may be proposed. The guidance office shall take action in letting the students realize that choosing a career is very significant. Thus, this calls for an action to continue and strengthen the project GABAY of San Pascual Senior High School 1.

Uplifting students career development is still in line with the general aim of project GABAY which is to provide holistic education despite of the threat of pandemic. Yet, academic/self-development domain and personal/social domain should not be neglected. These domains should likewise be included and incorporated to the project.

Matrix of Proposed Guidance Intervention Program on the Results of Needs Assessment Inventory Survey of San Pascual Senior High School 1 Grade 11 Students as Basis of Strengthening Project (GABAY) Guidance Advocacy and Building Adherence of the Youth

Specific Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Performance Indicator
To provide a basis for helping students and fully realize their best potentialities	Administration of student's individual inventory and anecdotal record form	2 nd week of the beginning of class (first semester)	Specific information with the students were identified.
To be able to attend to each member of the group and handle each individual effectively while dealing with the dynamics and goals of the group	Group counselling based on the results of needs assessment inventory survey	2 nd week of July (1 st semester)	Students will identify their strength and weaknesses through the different domains (Academic/Self Development, Career and Personal/Social Domain).

To realize the achiever qualities that are necessary to attain success	Presentation and implementation of the career guidance modules	August-September (1 st Semester)	Motivated students.
To develop self-regard or self-esteem.	Conduct bullying prevention and intervention	August-September (1 st semester)	Students realized their value and worth as a person
To nourish the spiritual life of the students	Bible study or prayer service	1 st week of September (1 st semester)	Students realized the importance of god in their everyday life specifically in achieving their academic goals.

Other Suggested Actions

- 1) The school may continue to conduct various orientations that will make the students ready in all aspects of their lives such as personal and career development orientation, tertiary education orientation and middle level skills orientation.
- 2) Integrating career guidance activities to selected subjects may be done to deepen student's appreciation on their developmental domains.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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